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61 ATTTTT TAACCA ATAGGC CGAAA ATCC CCGCAA AATCCC TTATA ATCAA AGAATA GACCGA
121 GATAGG GTTGAG TGTGTG TCCAGT TTGGAA CAAGAG TCCACT ATTTAA GAACGT GATCGA
181 CAACGT CAAAGG GCGAAA AACCGT CTATCA GGGCGA TGGCCC ACTACG TGAACC ATCACC
241 CTAATC AAGTTT TTTGGG GTCGAG GTGCCG TAAAGC ACTAAA TCGGAA CCCTAA AGGGAG
301 CCCCC ATTTAG AGCTTG ACGGGG AAAGCC GGC GAA CGTGGC GAGAAA GGAAGG GAAGAA
361 AGCGAA AGGAGC GGGCGC TAGGGC GCTGGC AAGTGT AGCGGT CACGCT GCGCGT AACCAC
421 CACACC CGCCGC GCTTAA TGCGCC GCTACA GGGCGC GTCCCA TTCGCC ATTCAG GCTGCG
481 CAACTG TTGGGA AGGGCG ATCGGT GCGGGC CTCCTC GCTATT ACGCCA GCTGGC GAAAGG
541 GGGATG TGCTGC AAGGCG ATTAAG TTGGGT AACGCC AGGGTT TTCCCA GTCACG ACGTTG
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661 GCCAGT CATTGT CCCTAC TCATTA CCTGCT ACTTAC ATGGTG AAAAAT CAAGAG TCGAGT
721 TAGGGA GGCAGT CATACC TTTTCA AGAGCG AATCCC ATTCAG GGTCGT CCTCTT AGTGTT
781 GTGGAA ACACAA GGCAGA ACTTAT CAGGTT TTAATA GCCAGA CTCATG TTGACA TGTAAA
841 TTATCA AAGATT TAGTGA GCTGGC ATAATF AGATFG AGAAAT AGCCCT TGTGGG TATGTG
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961 CTCTAA AAACAA AACAAA ACGATT TATTTT ATGTFG GTTGAT GTTTTG CCTGTA TGTCTG
1021 GTGCCC AGCAGA GGCTAA ATGAGG CCTTAG ATCCTC TAGAAC TGGAGT TACAGT TGGCAG
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1201 AGTGGG TCTGTT GAACTA CCTTCA GCAGCT GATTGG TGTCAG GATCAA ATTCAG GGTCTG
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1321 AGTTAA TAAACCA TATCCT CCCATF AAGTGC AGTCTC TCTTCC TTGGAG TACTGT CTGCAG
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1741 TCCAAC AATGGC TGCTA CCAATA GAAGGT TCAAGA ATTCAG TAGTTG TTCAGT CCATGA
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2521 GCTATG CCCGGC CCTGGC AAACAG AGAAGT GGATGC TCACAG TCAGCT ATTGGA TGGATC
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5581 GCGTCG ACACGT **ATAACT TCGTAT AATGTA TGCTAT ACGAAG TTATTA CTGCGT ACGAGC**
5641 **ATCGAT TGCCGT AAGAAG ATGGAA GAGGGC CCTGGG TCTCCT GGAGCT ATAGAC AGTTGA**
5701 **TGTGAG ATGCAT GACTCA GATCTT TTGGAA AAGCGG AAAGTG CTCTCA ACTTCA**
5761 **GAGCCA TCTCTC CAGCCT TAGCTC CTGACC TTTTAT TCTAGA AAAAA ATATTT GAGAAT**
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5941 **TTATAA TTTTGA GATTAT AAAGTC CTTGCT ACCTAT TTGGTG ATTCTT AGGTTA ATATA**
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6061 **CTTGCT AGCAGG TGACAT GTGGAA CTGTGG TCGGAC AAAAGT AGTATG ACGTGT CACCAC**
6121 **TTGTCT CCAAGT AATTAC TTGTAG CCCAGG CCGAGTA GACGTT GGAATG GCACAA ATGGTT**
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7621 TAACAG CACCCG TTTTCG GGTTTT CAGCAG TGTAC ATACAA GCTTTT ACAGCT TTCTGA
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7921 AAACCC CTCTAA TGTACC AGATTC CTCGGA AGTTAG AATTAA AAAGAT TAGGCA CACTTT
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8041 TTAATA TCTGAG CTCCTT TTCTGG GCTAGT GCTAAT GGACAA ATTAAC ATGGAA CTGCTG
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8161 GAATTT TATTTT ATGTGT ATGTGT GTTCTG CCTGCA CACATG TCTGTA CACCAT GAGAAC
8221 AGTGT CTGAGA GGCCAG AAGGTG TTGGGT CCCCTG GCACTG GAGCAC TGACTC TTTAAA
8281 GTTTTT CCTTTC TCCTGT CTAATT CACTTA AGCGTT AATCTT TGGGAA GTACAA TTAAGG
8341 GACTTT TGTCTC ACTGTA ACCCAG CCTCAG GCTAGA CCCTGA CTTTGC CCTGGG GACAGA
8401 GTATAA GCAGTG TTTGCT GAGATT ATCTGT TACTGA GCATGT TTGCCA AGTAGA GGCCTC
8461 TGAAGA TTATTA CATTG TTTTTT **GCAGCC TGGCAA TAGGTA CCATTA TCGGTC ACGCCC**
8521 **GGCACC GCCCAG ATCTCT GTGTCA TCTGGG TTGATG CTCATG CGGACA TTAATA CACCTC**
8581 **TCACCA CTGTAT CTGGAA ATATAC ATGGAC AGCCAC TTTCTT TTCTCA TCAAG AACTAC**
8641 **AAGACA AGGTAA GCAGGC CCAAAAT GAAAAAG GCTTGC ATGGTT ATGCTG GGGCTT TGAGAT**
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9181 ATTGTT TTGCAG CTGCCC TTCTAA ATCATC TCACTG GACAGT TTCCCT CCTAGC TCAGTT

LoxP site

Sequenced

Reverse Primer

Exon 3

Exon 4

9241 GTCCTG TGTCAC CTCAAC ATAGTG GACACG AAAGTG ACAGCA CATTCT TGGGAG CACATC
9301 TTAGTG AGAGTT AGGATT TCTGAC TGATCT GCTTCG TCCCTC TCTTCA CAGGTA CCACAA
9361 CTGCCA AGATTT TCCTGG ATCAAA CCTTGC CTCTCT CCCCCA AATATP GTGTAC ATTGGC
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9481 GTCCTG CCTGTT TTAGGT CAATCT AAAGGC AAGAGT CCCTAA ATATAC ATTAAA AGCTTT
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9601 TATTTT TCCATG AGAGAG ATTGAT CGACTT GGGATC CAGAAG GTGATG GAACAG **ACATTT**
9661 **GATCGG CTGATT GGC**AAAG **TAAGAA ATGACA TAAGCG TCTATT ATGTCT ATTTCT AGGTCT**
9721 **CAGGAG GAGGCG GGGCAG ACCCTG GGAGAG CAGCAG CACACT TAAGCC CATACC TTGGGC**
9781 **ATAGGA ATTCTA CTCTC AAGTAA AAGCAA AACATG TCTATG TATTTT CAAATC GTTTAG**
9841 **AAAGGC ATAGGA TCAATC ATAAAT CATATT CTTCTA GATTTG GGAGGG GTAAAG TCAGTG**
9901 **GCCCAT CCTGCT TCTCAT AAATTT GTTTTT GATTTT GTGACT TTTGAT GAGAAG CCTTCA**
9961 **TCACTG CTCCAG TGGTCC TGTTC TCCATA CTTTAT TACTGC TTCATC TGAGTT CTGTAT**
10021 **TAAGCA TAAAAA CACATG GTAGTC AGACTC ATTTTC CCAACA ATGGGG CTCTC TTTTGG**
10081 **GTGGTC AATATC AGAACT GCTGAT ATCGAA TTCCGA AGTTCC TATTCT CTAGAA AGTATA**
10141 **GGAACT TCAGGT CTGAAG AGGAGT TTACGT CCAGCC AAGCTA GCTTGG CTGCAG GTCGTC**
10201 **GAAATT CTACCG GGTAGG GGAGGC GCTTTT CCCAAG GCAGTC TGGAGC ATGCGC TTTAGC**
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10621 **CCGAAG GTCCTC CGGAGG CCCGGC ATTCTG CACGCT TCAAAA GCGCAC GTCTGC CGCGCT**
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10921 **CAGGGG CGCCCC GTTCTT TTTGTC AAGACC GACCTG TCCGGT GCCCTG AATGAA CTGCAG**
10981 **GACGAG GCAGCG CGGCTA TCGTGG CTGGCC ACGACG GCGGTT CCTTGC GCAGCT GTGCTC**
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13681 CTGCCT CCAAG TGGTGG GATTAA AGGTGC ACACCT CACAAC AGACAA GAGACC CTTTAG
13741 AAAGTA TTTAT ATGTGA GTATGT ATGACA AAGACA ACTTGT AGTTAG TGGCCT CTCTTC
13801 TACTCG TCGGTC TGAAAA TAGAAC TCGGGT TGTCTG ATTAGT GGCAGA AGCATT TACCCT

Exon 5

Exon 6

Forward Primer

Sequenced

△
(1794 bases)

LoxP site

13861 CTGAGC CACCAC CAGTCA TGTAAG GAACCC TTACCT AGATGG AAAAGA AATGGG GATTGG
13921 GTCCTT ATAGTC TGCTAG AACCTT AGGGGA GACCGG CCTATT AAATCT GACTGT AGGAAG
13981 ACAGAC FTAGAC CTGCAA ACATAA ATATTG CAACGG TCTTTC AGTTAA CAGTGA ACTTAA
14041 AACATT TCTGTT ACTTCA TTCAAG AGGGAT TAATAA ACTTTG CAAGCA GTTGTG TGTCTG
14101 TGTTC CTTGTT TTGCTG ACATTG TCAACA AAGATA GCAATT TGCTTA AACTAA CCTGTA
14161 GGATGG CAATAG TCTGGA AACATA GGCAAT ATATAT TTTTGA TGGTGC AAACCC TCCTGA
14221 TTCCTA CTTAGG ATATAG TAGAGA TACTAG GTTCAA CCATTG GGAATA AGACAC AACTCA
14281 CAAGCT GGGCTT GGTGGC GCACGC CTTTAA TCCCAA CACTCG GGAGTC AGAGGC AGGCGG
14341 ATTTCT GAGTTC GAGGCC AGCCTG GTCTAC AAAGTG AGTTCC AGGACA GCCAGG GCTATA
14401 CAGAGA AACCTT GTCTTG AAAAAC CATAAA AAAAGA AAAAAA GACTCA ACTCAC TAGGGA
14461 CACAGG TTCCTG GGCAGG AAATGA TGACAA TGAATG GTTAACT ATCCTT AGTTAC TGTAAT
14521 TTTATA TAATAC ACTCAA CTATGC ATCACT AAGATT GTAAGA AACACT GGAGAG TTTGTC
14581 ATGTAC CATAGT GTAATA TAAATG AACCAT TAGGTA TTAGAA TATACC TTATAT ATATAT
14641 ATATAC TTTATA GTCAGC CTAAT ATTCTT AAATAC TTGTGA TATTTA ATTTTA GTTTAT
14701 TCAGAT CACTAT TTAAAG GGTAGA FTAACC CAGAGT AAGTGT TAGGAA CTCGCG GAAGTA
14761 GGCCAG ATAAGG AGGGAT CGAAGT GGAAGG CAGCTG TAGATT AAGTTC TTTCTC TCAGCC
14821 TACCCC AAACAA AGGACC AGTGCT GAGGAC TTGGGC ACGAAC TCCCTA GGATCG CCCGGG
14881 TTGATT CGAGGC TGCTAA CAAATC GAGCAG TGTGGT TTTCAA GAGGAA GCAAAA AGCCTC
14941 TCCACC CAGGCC TGGAA TTTTCC ACCCAA TGTCTG CAGATG TGGTTT TGCAAG AGGAAG
15001 CAAAAA GCCTCT CCACCC AGGCCT GGAATG TTTCCA CCCAAT GTCGAG CAAACC CCGCCC
15061 AGCGTC TTGTCA TTGGCG AATTCG AACACG CAGATG CAGTCG GGGCGG CGCGGT CCCAGG
15121 TCCACT TCGCAT ATTAAG GTGACG CGTGTG GCCTCG AACACC GAGCGA CCCTGC AGCGAC
15181 CGCCTT AACAGC GTCAAC AGCGTG CCGCAG ATCTTG GTGGCG TGAAC TCCCGC ACCTCT
15241 TCGGCC AGCGCC TTGTAG AAGCGC GTGCCA TGGATC CTGATG ATGTTG TTTGAT CTCTTA
15301 AATCTT TTGTGA TGGAAA ACTTTT CTTCGT ACCACG GGACTA AACCTG GTTATG TAGATT
15361 CCATTC AAAAAA GTATA AAAAGC CAAAAT CTGGTA CACAAG GAAATT ATGACG ATGATT
15421 GGAAAG GGTTTT ATAGTA CCGACA ATAAAT ACGACG CTGCGG GATACT CTGTAG ATAATG
15481 AAAACC CGCTCT CTGGAA AAGCTG GAGGCG TGGTCA AAGTGA CGTATC CAGGAC TGACGA
15541 AGGTTT TCGCAC TAAAAG TGGATA ATGCCG AAACCTA TTAAGA AAGAGT TAGGTT TAAGTC
15601 TCACCT AACCGT TGATGG AGCAAG TCGGAA CCGAAG AGTTTA TCAAAA GGTTTC GTGATG
15661 GTGCTT CGCGTG TAGTGC TCAGCC TTTCCCT TCGCTG AGGGGA GTTCTA CGCTTG AATATA
15721 TTAATA ACTGGG AACAGG CGAAAAG CGTTAA CGCTAG AACTTG AGATTA ATTTTG AAAACC
15781 GTGGAA AACGTG GCCAAG ATGCGA TGTATG AGTATA TGGCTC AAGCCT GTGACG GAAATC
15841 GTGTCA GCGCAT CTCCTT GTGAAG GAACCT TACTTC TGTGGT GTGACA TAATTG GACAAA
15901 CTACCT ACAGAG ATTTAA AGCTCT AAGTGA AATATA AAATTT TTAAGT GTATAA TGTGTT
15961 AAACCTA CTGATT CTAATT GTTTGT GTATTT TAGATT CCAACC TATGGA ACTGAT GAATGG
16021 GAGCAG TGGTGG AATGCA GATCCT AGAGCT CGCTGA TCAGCC TCGACT GTGCTT TCTAGT
16081 TGCCAG CCATCT GTTGTG TGCCCC TCCCCC GTGCCT TCCTTG ACCCTG GAAGGT GCCACT
16141 CCCACT GTCCTT TCCTAA TAAAAT GAGGAA ATTGCA TCGCAT TGTCTG AGTAGG TGTAT
16201 TCTATT CTGGGG GGTGGG GTGGGG CAGGAC AGCAAG GGGGAG GATTGG GAAGAC AATAGC
16261 AGGCAT GCTGGG GATGCG GTGGGC TCTATG GCTTCT GAGGCG GAAAGA ACCAGC CCGGGC
16321 GGTGGA GCTCCA GCTTTT GTTCCC TTTAGT GAGGGT TAATTT CGAGCT TGCGGT AATCAT
16381 GGTGAT AGCTGT TTTCTG TGTGAA ATTTGT ATCCCG TCACAA TTCCAC ACAACA TACGAT
16441 CCGGAA CATAAA AGTGTA AAGCCT GGGGTG CCTAAT GAGTGA GCTAAC TCACAT TAATTG
16501 CGTTGC GCTCAC TGCCCG CTTTCC AGTCGG GAAACC TGTCTG GCCAGC TGCATT AATGAA
16561 TCGGCC AACGCG CGGGGA GAGGCG GTTTGC GTATTG GGCCTC CTTCGG CTTCCT CGCTCA
16621 CTGACT CGCTGC GCTCGG TCGTTC GGCTGC GGCAG CCGTAT CAGCTC ACTCAA AGGCGG
16681 TAATAA GGTATT CACAGG AATCAG GGGATA ACGCAG GAAAGA ACATGT GAGCAA AAGGCC
16741 AGCAAA AGGCCA GGAACC GTAAAA AGGCCG CGTTGC TGGCGT TTTTCC ATAGGC TCCGCC
16801 CCCTTG ACGAGC ATCACA AAAATC GACGCT CAAGTC AGAGGT GGCGAA ACCCGA CAGGAC
16861 TATAAA GATACC AGGCTT TTCCCC CTGGAA GCTCCC TCGTGC GCTCTC CTGTTT CGACCC
16921 TGCCCG TTACCG GATACC TGTCCG CCTTTC TCCCTT CGGGAA GCGTGG CGCTTT CTCATA
16981 GCTCAC GCTGTA GGTATC TCAGTT CGGTGT AGGTCG TTCGCT CCAAGC TGGGCT GTGTGC
17041 ACGAAC CCCCGG TTCAGC CCGACC GCTGCG CCTTAT CCGGTA ACTATC GTCTTG AGTCCA
17101 ACCCGG TAAGAC ACGACT TATCGC CACTGG CAGCAG CCACTG GTAACA GGATTA GCAGAG
17161 CGAGGT ATGTAG GCGGTG CTACAG AGTTCT TGAAGT GGTGGC CTAACCT ACGGCT ACACCTA
17221 GAAGAA CAGTAT TTGGTA TCTGCG CTCTGC TGAAGC CAGTTA CCTTCG GAAAAA GAGTTG
17281 GTAGCT CTTGAT CCGGCA AACAAA CCACCG CTGGTA GCGGTG GTTTTT TTGTTT GCAAGC
17341 AGCAGA TTACGC GCAGAA AAAAAG GATCTC AAGAAG ATCCTT TGATCT TTTCTA CGGGGT
17401 CTGACG CTCAGT GGAACG AAAAAT CACGTT AAGGGA TTTTGG TCATGA GATTAT CAAAAA
17461 GGATCT TCACCT AGATCC TTTTAA ATTTAA AATGAA GTTTTA AATCAA TCTAAA GTATAT
17521 ATGAGT AAACCT GGTCTG ACAGTT ACCAAT GCTTAA TCAGTG AGGCAC CTATCT CAGCGA
17581 TCTGTC TATTTT GTTACT CCATAG TTGCCT GACTCC CCGTCT GTGAGA TAACTA CGATAC
17641 GGGAGG GCTTAC CATCTG GCCCCA GTGCTG CAATGA TACCGC GAGACC CACGCT CACCCG
17701 CTCCAG ATTTAT CAGCAA TAAACC AGCCAG CCGGAA GGGCCG AGCGCA GAAGTG GTCCTG
17761 CAACTT TATCCG CCTCCA TCCAGT CTATTA ATTTGT GCGGGG AAGCTA GAGTAA GTAGTT
17821 CGCCAG TTAATA GTTTGC GCAACC TTGTTG CCATTG CTACAG GCATCG TGGTGT CACGCT
17881 CGTCTG TTTGTA TGGCTT CATTCA GCTCCG GTTCCC AACGAT CAAGCT CAGTTA CATGAT
17941 CCCCCA TGTGTT GCAAAA AAGCGG TTAGCT CCTTCG GTCCTC CGATCG TTGTCA GAAGTA
18001 AGTTGG CCGCAG TGTGAT CACTCA TGGTTA TGGCAG CACTGC ATAATT CTCTTA CTGTCA
18061 TGCCAT CCGTAA GATGCT TTTCTG TGACTG GTGAGT ACTCAA CCAAGT CATTCG GAGAA
18121 AGTGTA TGCGGC GACCGA GTTGCT CTTGCC CCGCGT CAATAC GGGATA ATACCC CACCAC
18181 ATAGCA GAACTT TAAAAG TGCTCA TCATTG GAAAAC GTTCTT CGGGGC GAAAAC TCTCAA
18241 GGATCT TACCGC TGTGTA GATCCA GTTCTG TGTAA CCACTC GTGCAC CCAACT GATCTT
18301 CAGCAT CTTTAA CTTTCA CCAGCG TTTCTG GGTGAG CAAAAA CAGGAA GGCAAA ATGCCG
18361 CAAAAA AGGGAA TAAGGG CGACAC GGAATG GTTGAA TACTCA TACTCT TCCTTT TTTCAAT
18421 ATTATT GAAGCA TTTATC AGGGTT ATTGTC TCATGA GCGGAT ACATAT TTGAAT GTATTT

18481 AGAAAA ATAAAC AAATAG GGGTTC CGCGCA CATTTC CCCGAA AAGTGC CAC